

Bibliometric Analysis of Studies Published on Alternative Tourism in Tourism Literature

Elif BAK ATEŞ¹

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ABSTRACT

The ever-growing and changing tourism sector offers alternative touristic products and promote. In parallel with the developments in the world, besides coastal tourism shaped by the sea-sand-sun trio, many alternative tourism types are coming out in Turkey. In the study, it is aimed to examine the bibliometric profiles of the articles titled “alternative tourism” within the framework of the determined parameters. In this context, the articles published between 2000-2022 were derived from the Google Scholar database. 42 articles accessed as a result of the searches lay with different variables with frequency analysis and graphics. The articles were examined on the basis of criteria such as the year they were published, the journal they were published in, the research method and research variables. As a result of this evaluation, it was seen that the most articles on alternative tourism were published in 2008. It has been determined that the research variables are mostly alternative tourism potential and centers. Theoretical studies are relatively more numerous than empirical studies. In terms of the findings, it is thought that the study will provide an important and comprehensive resource that researchers can benefit from. Other findings of the study show that the number of studies on alternative tourism has increased in recent years.

1. Introduction

The change in tourist expectations over time, the desire to get away from noise and urban life, the expectation of a more natural life and higher quality service have brought forward different searching for tourists. As a result of these searchings, the concept of alternative tourism emerged, the undergoing vacation conception has changed and different and new types of tourism have come out (Ulusan & Batman, 2010). Increasing awareness of tourists, local people and other tourism stakeholders about the negative effects of mass tourism is also one of the reasons that strengthen the emergence of alternative tourism (Jovičić, 2016). Therefore, it can be stated that the emergence of alternative tourism is related to criticism of mass tourism and its negative effects on destinations (Christou, 2012).

Based on sustainability, the development of alternative tourism types, which adopt an understanding that is responsive to the environment, nature and cultural resources, is also reflected in the academic literature. Many articles on alternative tourism have been written and published in scientific journals. One of the frequently

¹ PhD, Professional Tour Guide, Ordu, Turkey; elifb.0052@gmail.com

preferred techniques for classifying and evaluating scientific publications within certain criteria is bibliometric analysis. In bibliometric research, scientific findings are obtained by evaluating and analyzing certain qualities of documents or publications (Ulu & Akdağ, 2015). More clearly, collecting statistical data about the author, subject, citation and sources with bibliometric studies. In the light of these statistical data, a general situation assessment can be made for a certain field (Çetinkaya Bozkurt & Çetin, 2016).

In this study, it is aimed to evaluate the articles titled “alternative tourism” published in the YÖK Academic database with a bibliometric approach. In this context, findings about the relevant literature and bibliometric analysis are included in the study. Bibliometrics has a remarkable feature in terms of summarizing many previous studies in a single study. In addition, the objectivity of the bibliometric approach is important in the sense that it evaluates the situation of the area more rigorous (Ruhanen et al., 2015). The development of alternative tourism and the increase in the number of researches makes it necessary to synthesize these publications in a single study. In this study, the profile of the studies in the alternative tourism literature has been revealed. It is thought that bibliometric studies on different sub-topics of tourism will contribute to the literature and will be a guide for future studies.

2. Literature Review

Alternative tourism is defined as tourism types that should be developed by adhering to nature-sensitive and sustainable principles (Baytok et al., 2017). With the definition of Akoğlan Kozak and Bahçe (2009), alternative tourism that includes touristic products and services that reduce the effects of mass tourism, contribute to the increase of welfare levels by distributing tourism incomes in a balanced way and giving priority to the local people, and spreading the income flow from tourism to wider time and segments. variety. The idea of alternative tourism comes into prominence as a solution model that enables the planning and execution of today’s tourism activities without compromising the right of use of future generations, and in this context, it also guides future tourism developments (Duran & Özkul, 2018). On the other hand, unplanned, unbalanced development and unequal distribution of the benefits provided by the stakeholders, especially the local people, are seen as important issues that pave the way for the emergence of alternative tourism (Baytok et al., 2017). The desire of those participating in tourism to have a different experience, to discover new things and to see new things has also increased the importance of alternative tourism (Çeken et al., 2012). Another reason that increases the interest in alternative tourism types is that it spreads throughout the year and appeals to different target groups (Zengin & Sancar, 2014).

Alternative tourism that have characteristics that require small-scale, low-level investment, require high participation of local people, minimize negative effects on local people, and involve local people in decisions (Triarchi & Karamanis, 2017). It also contain within itself different types that support social and ecological

transformations such as pro-poor tourism, community-based tourism, voluntary tourism, eco-tourism, and sustainable tourism (Isaac, 2010). Alternative tourism types are engaged in a sensitive approach that gives priority to natural and cultural resources during the planning and development phase (Triarchi & Karamanis, 2017). In summary, some of the typical features of alternative tourism are that it is based on social and environmental sensitivity, requires awareness of going back to nature and protecting nature, involving local people in tourism activities, featuring on the sale of local products, and generating employment for local people.

3. Methodology

In this study, Turkish articles titled “alternative tourism” were analyzed with a bibliometric approach, YÖK Academic database was used and the literature with the keywords “alternative tourism” was reviewed. As a result of the scans, 42 articles published between 2000-2022 were presented with various variables with the help of frequency analysis and tables. Articles, the year they were published, the journal in which they were published, the research method and the research variables were examined on the basis of criteria.

Bibliometrics is the analysis of academic literature using statistical methods (Ruhanen et. al., 2015). By the definition of Özel and Kozak (2012), bibliometrics is a method in which studies published in a specific field are analyzed through quantitative analysis. In bibliometric research, findings related to scientific communication are reached by analyzing certain features of documents or publications (Al & Çoştur, 2007). Analysis uses a quantitative approach to observe, evaluate, and describe published work. These methods require a systematic, transparent and repeatable review process, which increases the quality of the reviews (Zupic & Čater, 2015). At the same time, it makes it possible for researchers to know and introduce disciplines better and to have an idea about the status of the area (Al & Çoştur, 2007). With this method, published studies related to a field. It is examined in the context of criteria such as the year, subject, number of authors and bibliography, citations, the journal in which it was published, and the research method used. Besides, with these studies, the most productive authors who publish on a subject can be identified, while the level of interaction between them can be determined (Ulu & Akdağ, 2015).

While making bibliometric analysis of a field, it is essential to evaluate the existing databases first and their suitability, that is, interpreting the results of one or the other (Sanchez et al., 2017). Although these methods are not new, they have gained attention with the proliferation of easily accessible databases (Zupic & Cater, 2015). Depending on the developments, it has been frequently started to used in different fields in the literature.

3.1. Bibliometric studies

The term bibliometrics was first used by Groos and Pritchard (1969). It is defined as the application of mathematical and statistical methods to books and other

means of communication. Synthesizing the findings of previous research in a field seems essential for a field of research to flourish. Accordingly, the use of bibliometrics in tourism research is increasing day by day (Hall, 2011; Özel & Kozak, 2012). Later, it is seen that the studies are spreaded to many sub-branches of tourism and bibliometric studies were carried out on these subjects.

In addition to the studies evaluating the concept of alternative tourism from a conceptual perspective, bibliometric studies on subjects such as alternative tourism opportunities and potential, alternative tourism activities and resources, alternative tourism types and centers, sustainable tourism, rural tourism, ecotourism are some of the studies mentioned. However, it is seen that there are also studies in which tourism journals are examined with a bibliometric approach.

In parallel with these developments, many studies using the bibliometric approach have also been published in the national tourism literature. Çiçek and Kozak (2012) presented a bibliometric profile of the journals published in *Anatolia Journal of Tourism Research*. Özel and Kozak (2012) analyzed the articles published in peer-reviewed journals and written in the field of tourism marketing according to bibliometric features and citations in the articles. In the study of Zencir and Kozak (2012), the bibliometric profile of the articles on tourism in the journals published by the Social Sciences Institutes in Turkey was obtained. The articles were evaluated on the basis of criteria such as publication year, subject, language, number of authors, number of pages, number of sources used. When the studies are examined, it is seen that bibliometric studies concentrate on theses and articles published in selected journals. In her study, Güçlü Nergiz (2014) examined the master's and doctoral theses that prepared in the field of tourism in Turkey between the years 1990-2013.

In their study, Toksöz and Birdir (2016) reviewed the graduate theses of the years 2006-2015 with the keywords "cultural heritage" and examined the bibliometric features of a total of 84 graduate theses.

Aydın (2017), on the other hand, examined the theses written in the field of food and beverage in terms of some bibliometric features. Yılmaz (2017) examined the articles dealing with the subject of tipping between 1978 and 2015 according to criteria such as years, journals, topics, citations, data collection methods, and sample group. Düşmezkalender and Metin (2019) examined the articles titled alternative tourism published between 2000-2018 in terms of some bibliometric features. In the study of Boyraz and Kabakulak (2020), scientific publications of academicians working in institutions providing higher education education in the field of tourism guidance were examined in terms of various parameters. Çetiner (2022) revealed the general characteristics and changes in the historical process with the bibliometric analysis method of the studies on sports tourism. For this purpose, 1948 articles published in the journals reviewed in the Scopus database between 1967-2022 were examined. Ünüvar and Yurtlu (2022) determined the bibliometric profile of a total of 104 peer-reviewed articles published in 2018, 2019 and 2020 in the *Journal of Travel and Hotel Management*, which was determined to have the highest impact factor in 2019 among the academic journals in the tourism literature in Turkey. Tozoğlu and

Uçar (2022) aimed to determine the bibliometric features of articles on tourism and leadership. For this purpose, bibliometric analysis of 502 articles on tourism and leadership reviewed in the field of business management and social sciences from the Scopus database was carried out using R-Studio software.

4. Results and Discussion

The distribution of the years in which the articles with the title of alternative tourism were published are shown in Fig. 1. It is seen that the most relevant studies were published in 2008 (7 articles), followed by 2014 (5 articles). While 1 article was published in the last 4 years (2019, 2020, 2021, 2022), this number reached 3 articles in 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012.

Fig. 1. Frequency of articles by years

Source: Author's elaboration

The journals in which 42 articles on alternative tourism were published were examined and this distribution is shown in Fig. 2. Articles on the subject have been published in 37 different journals. It has been determined that the first 6 journals with the highest number of articles published 2 articles. These journals were determined as JOTAGS, Atatürk University Journal of Social Sciences Institute, International Journal of Social and Economic Sciences, Gaziantep University Journal of Social Sciences, Journal of Current Researches on Social Sciences and Eurasian Journal of Social and Economic Research (EJRSE).

Fig. 2. Frequency of articles according to journals in which they were published
Source: Author's elaboration

The distribution of the research types of the articles by years is shown in Fig. 3. Most of the studies in the field of alternative tourism consisted of theoretical studies (32 articles), and the most theoretical studies (7 articles) were done in 2008. Then the year 2014 (5 articles) followed. On the other hand, it can be said that empirical studies (10 articles) intensified in 2010 and 2018.

Fig. 3. Frequency of type of research
Source: Author's elaboration

The topics covered in the articles are expressed in Fig. 4. Subject headings were evaluated with a general approach, and similar subject headings were gathered under one title. “Alternative tourism potential/possibilities and effects/alternative tourism activities/resources” (17 articles) is one of the most studied topics in the field of alternative tourism. However, in the second place, alternative tourism centers and their resources (7 articles) have often been the subject of articles. In addition to the studies that include the concept of alternative tourism (6 articles), alternative tourism routes are among the alternative tourism types, ecotourism/ecological farms, sustainable tourism, rural tourism (2 articles), adventure tourism, gastronomic tourism, health tourism and geological heritage areas (1 article) are among the other topics that are examined.

Fig. 3. Frequency of subjects of the articles
Source: Author's elaboration

5. Conclusion

In this study, we aimed to examine the articles titled “alternative tourism” in the YÖK Academic database in terms of bibliometric features. The 42 articles that were accessed were examined within the framework of certain parameters. In the 2023 Tourism Strategy of Turkey it is mentioned that the transportation network between destinations should be improved and also travel opportunities in order to develop alternative tourism (www.kuzka.gov.tr). This increasing awareness of the development of alternative tourism shows itself in the literature in parallel with the application areas.

Considering the criteria examined in the articles, according to the years, it is seen that the most articles were published in 2008, and respectively second place in 2014. It has been seen that the alternative tourism potentials of the most sampled

regions and their possible effects on the region have been revealed. It is seen that alternative tourism centers and resources, ecotourism and ecofarms, which are tourism types made within the scope of applied alternative tourism.

Considering the methods of the researches, in 2014 ecological, economic and culturally suitable areas for some alternative tourism activities that can be done in Isparta Province were determined by using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) tools. In order to achieve this aim, the Conformity Class Values method was used. Methods such as observation, interview, document review and case study were used in the study, in which the potential of an alternative ecotourism center named "Lisinia nature", which operated in the province of Burdur in 2017 and is planned to be evaluated within the scope of tourism in the near future, is revealed. In the 2019 and 2020 studies the SWOT analysis method was preferred. These findings show that different methods have been used in recent years.

In the International Journal of Social and Economic Sciences, which is among the first six journals published by studies titled alternative tourism, the factors affecting the development of rural tourism, which is one of the alternative tourism types, and the effects of rural tourism are discussed theoretically.

Considering the last 5 years in which the articles were published, it was seen that the studies had a wide range of different alternative tourism types (adventure tourism) and alternative tourism routes (Kurtalan Express and Kral Road route). Especially in recent years, studies on nature-based tourism and protected areas have been given priority.

Since the research is limited to the articles in the YÖK Academic database, studies in different databases could not be included in the research. It can be suggested that future studies should be carried out by including different databases in the research. On the other hand, it can be considered as a limitation that the research is carried out only with articles with the title of alternative tourism. Including books, theses and papers, more comprehensive bibliometric studies can be done.

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